

Paper 15

FACTORS EFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF SOLAR PANEL AND CHALLENGES TO IMPROVE THE SAME

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Abstract

The power requirement in India is satisfied using the conventional and non conventional methods. Using conventional methods the country is not in a position to fulfill the requirement of the power demand. The conventional method of power production causes environmental pollution which is another challenge. This led to the invention of the power production using non conventional methods. Today the country is promoting more and more power production through such non conventional methods like solar energy plants, wind energy plants, tidal energy plants etc. These energy production plants are eco friendly and they do not contribute to the environmental pollutions. The major renewable energy plant in India providing energy requirements is the solar energy. The solar plants use Photo voltaic cells which convert sunlight into electricity. The major problem faced in such solar plant are the panel efficiency. The solar panel efficiency is found to be in between 18% to 20%. This paper contains the reason for the low solar panel efficiency and the methods to be implemented to improve the solar panel efficiency. This paper also contains the methods to be followed in improving the solar panel efficiency at the manufacturing end, the cost involved in improving the efficiency of the solar panel and easy methods in improving the efficiency of solar panel at the installation site with the available panels.

Key words: Solar panel, Efficiency, Conventional, Non conventional, Renewable energy, Solar plant.

1. Introduction

The invention of photo voltaic cell was done in the year 1839 by Alexandre Edmond Becquerel. [1] In his invention he claimed that when an electrode is exposed to sunlight when submerged inside a conductive solution creates an electric current. This invention has brought a new avenue in the electric energy generation where the sun light is found to be in abandonment. The electrical energy generated from this above technology is known as solar energy. This form of energy is considered to be non polluting renewable energy.[2] The use of solar energy is getting more and more popular in 21st century. This is due to the scarcity of the raw materials for the conventional electric generation plants as well as the amount of pollution contributed to the environment. The demand for solar energy is still increasing due to the increase in population. During February 2018 the total amount of electrical energy generated through the solar energy is 20 GW.[3]. The present government is entertaining many investors towards solar energy plants. Due to this we are able to find more and more solar energy plants in India. Today we are able to find out may commercial solar plants as well as decentralized solar plants working in different houses.

1.1 Factors effecting the efficiency

Solar energy mainly suffers from the efficiency in the solar photo voltaic cells.[4] Normally the solar cells are able to generate 20% efficient power. One square meters of sunlight is suppose to generate one kilowatt of energy where in due to problem in the efficiency it is generating only 200W. The major factors effecting the efficiency of the solar panels are

- Raise in temperature of the solar panel (Thermodynamic efficiency) reduces the performance of the solar panel. The PN Junction suffers in generating electrons due to raise in temperature.[5] The temperature coefficient of solar panel is -0.4 to -0.5.
- Shockley and Queisser effect reduces the efficiency of the photo voltaic cells. Due to this effect the photon below a certain band instead of generating electrons in PN junction converts the photon into heat.[6] This is called ultimate efficiency issue.
- The energy loss due to Quantum efficiency. In this case the energy gets lost due to short circuit condition. Here the reflection of light from the surface of the photo voltaic cell is also responsible for the energy loss.[7]
- The maximum power output variation depends on various factors. The output power depends on the resistive load, the heat dissipation in various sides like incident sun light, conducting wires and load. The power output varies if load resistance is increased. The power loss will be more if the wires carrying the current from the solar panel to battery backup is long enough and having more diameter than required.
- Solar cell's fill factor is another limiting factor for the efficiency. Here the efficiency is limited by the cell series, shunt resistance and loses in the diode. [8]
- Air mass effects the efficiency of solar panel. Here the airmass in the atmosphere filters the sun light incident on the solar cell. [9]

1.2 The challenges to improve the efficiency.

The 20% efficiency in the solar panel has a lot of challenges for the improvements. The challenges include the improvements in the solar cell design, panel installation, working on reducing the heat and usage of proper conductors for the energy supply as well as the internal

connectivity of the solar cells.[10] Certain challenges are in the cell design and manufacture side. Other challenges are in the installation side.

One of the problems in improving the efficiency is to reduce the temperature. This can be done at the installation stage. The Schockley and Queisser effect is difficult to eliminate as we do not have any control over the incident sunlight in different bands. The loss due to quantum efficiency can be reduced. The power loss due to maximum power output can be reduce by selection of proper materials at the installation site. The energy loss due to fill factor can be reduced in the manufacturing plants by proper cell joints and looking into shunt resistance. The power loss due to airmass effect is unavoidable.

2. Objective

The objective of this paper is to identify the reasons for the 20% efficiency in the solar panels and to propose a model to improve the efficiency for the better productions. The objective also includes the improvement strategies to be implemented by the manufacturer as well as at the installation sites.

3. Methodology.

The methodology includes the statement of the factor effecting the efficiency of the solar panel and the model to improve the efficiency in a tabular form.

Table 1. Factors effecting the solar panel efficiency and the use of model to improve the same.

Sl. No	Factor Effecting the efficiency	Model to increase the efficiency	Manufacturer/ Installation
1.	Raise in Temperature	Reduce the temperature by increasing the hight of the panel installation from the ground level Installthe panel where cross ventillation is avilable which reduces the temperature.	Installation No much additional cost is involved in setting up the panels.
2.	Schockley and Queisser effect	Use of nano structured solar cells will improve the efficiency by nearly 42%	Manufacturer
3.	The energy loss due to Quantum efficiency.	This can be avoided using a short circuit protector designed by the inverter system	Inverter manufaturer

4.	The maximum power output variation	Use of current latest equipments like LED bulbs, Fans and other equipments which offer less resistive load	Installation sites
5.	Solar cell's fill factor	The manufacturing firms need to have high level equipments for manufacturing solar panels by connecting solar cells without any scope for impurities from outside and proper connection to avoid capacitance between the connectors	Manufacturer
6.	Air mass effects	Unavoidable	

4. Analysis.

The concept of increasing the efficiency of the solar panel is difficult to achieve as the major factor effecting the efficiency is the solar cell, the PN junction and its performance. This can be solved by using the latest concept of nano technology in developing the solar cells. The use of nano technology being a new trend in the manufacturing industry increases the cost of the solar panel. Today the conventional monolithic solar panel is available for Rs 45 per watt. But the same panel designed using the nano technology is still in the research lab and researchers are trying to get a low cost nano structured thin film solar panels to the market. The efficiency of such nano structured thin film solar panels is expected to be around 42%. The other factors like energy loss due to Quantum efficiency and maximum power output variation are related to the resistivity in the load and short circuit current loss can be minimized using controller designs and use of equipments which offer very less resistance.

5. Conclusion

The solar panel efficiency which is almost 20% can be increased to around 42% by using the various suggestions given in the model. However most of the factors effecting the efficiency are related to the PN junction of the solar panel the solution to this is the use of the nano structured solar cells. Today the nano structured solar cells are still in the research lab. Researchers are working on how to design the low cost nano structured solar panels. As long as the above said panels come to the market it is difficult to achieve the higher efficiency in the solar panel. However the factors like raise in the temperature, quantum efficiency, maximum power output variation can be controlled at the installation site as proposed by the model can increase the efficiency.

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